

Drug Interactions and Drug Interaction Checkers

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INTRODUCTION

Because individuals are living longer and accruing chronic diseases, practitioners have a new responsibility to prescribe appropriately the many medications available to manage concurrent disease states. The plethora of pharmaceutical options must be balanced with the potential risk of multiple medication use. These risks include, but are not limited to, adverse effects, drug/drug interactions, drug/disease interactions and inappropriate dosing regimens. Primary care health professionals such as physicians, physician assistants, and nurses have an enormous opportunity to survey patients for this risk given their accessibility and roles in the coordination of care (1).

While the most commonly used definition of polypharmacy is being on five or more medicines, definitions are variable, which can cause confusion for researchers as well as clinicians in practice. Numerical definitions of polypharmacy do not account for specific comorbidities present and make it difficult to assess safety and appropriateness of therapy in the clinical setting. There is a need for an internationally agreed definition of polypharmacy. The results indicate the need for a shift towards the term ‘appropriate polypharmacy’ using a holistic approach of assessing medication use in context of comorbidities present, according to best available evidence in order to optimize health outcomes (2). I prefer the definition of **polypharmacy (polytherapy)** as the necessary and justified use of multiple medication (5 or more drugs), whilst **polypragmasia (polypragmasy)** would be the term for the inappropriate use of multiple drugs that includes one of the errors: too many medications, duplication of medications, dangerous drug-drug interactions or drug-disease interactions, and excessive duration of pharmacotherapy.

Patients, especially elderly and chronically ill, visit more than one physician. Sometimes physicians do not pay attention on the drugs prescribed by other physician, and that is one of the reasons why dangerous drug/drug interactions or drug/disease interactions can occur. The role of general practitioners and family doctors is very important in coordinating polypharmacy and checking all the interactions between prescribed drugs, as well as over-the-counter (OTC) drugs. Another cause of drug/drug interactions is self-medication. Patients rarely mention to their primary care and other physicians, if they are using OTC drugs, and physicians often forget to ask about it. Third reason for polypharmacy is lack of time. Physicians, both primary care physicians and hospital specialists, are often overloaded with work and have too many patients, so they do not have enough time for detailed pharmacological anamnesis.

DRUG INTERACTIONS

Drug interactions are changes in a drug's effects due to recent or concurrent use of another drug or drugs (drug-drug interactions), ingestion of food (drug-nutrient interactions), or ingestion of dietary supplements (dietary supplement-drug interactions).

A drug-drug interaction may increase or decrease the effects of one or both drugs. Clinically significant interactions are often predictable and usually undesired. Adverse effects or therapeutic failure may result. Rarely, clinicians can use predictable drug-drug interactions to produce a desired therapeutic effect. For example, co-administration of lopinavir and ritonavir to patients with HIV infection results in altered metabolism of lopinavir and increases serum lopinavir concentrations and effectiveness. In therapeutic duplication, two drugs with similar properties are taken at the same time and have additive effects. For example, taking a benzodiazepine for anxiety and another benzodiazepine at bedtime for insomnia may have a cumulative effect, leading to toxicity. In **pharmacodynamic interactions**, one drug alters the sensitivity or responsiveness of tissues to another drug by having the same (agonistic) or a blocking (antagonistic) effect. These effects usually occur at the receptor level but may occur intracellularly. In **pharmacokinetic interactions**, a drug usually alters absorption, distribution, protein binding, metabolism, or excretion of another drug. Thus, the amount and persistence of available drug at receptor sites change. Pharmacokinetic interactions alter magnitude and duration, not type, of effect. They are often predicted based on knowledge of the individual drugs or detected by monitoring drug concentrations or clinical signs (3).

Nutrient-Drug Interactions

Foods can enhance, delay, or decrease drug absorption. Foods impair absorption of many antibiotics. They can alter metabolism of drugs. For example, high-protein diets can accelerate metabolism of certain drugs by stimulating cytochrome P-450. Eating grapefruit can inhibit cytochrome P-450 3A4, slowing metabolism of some drugs (amiodarone, carbamazepine, cyclosporine, certain calcium channel blockers). Diets that alter the bacterial flora may markedly affect the overall metabolism of certain drugs. Some foods affect the body's response to drugs. For example, tyramine, a component of cheese and a potent vasoconstrictor, can cause hypertensive crisis in some patients who take monoamine oxidase inhibitors and eat cheese. Nutritional deficiencies can affect drug absorption and metabolism. Severe energy and protein deficiencies reduce enzyme tissue concentrations and may impair the response to drugs by reducing absorption or protein binding and causing liver dysfunction. Changes in the gastrointestinal tract can impair absorption and affect the response to a drug. Deficiency of calcium, magnesium, or zinc may impair drug metabolism. Vitamin C deficiency decreases activity of drug-metabolizing enzymes, especially in older people (4).

Transporter-Mediated Drug-Drug Interactions

Drug transporters are considered to be determinants of drug disposition and effects/toxicities by affecting the absorption, distribution, and excretion of drugs. Drug transporters are generally divided into solute carrier (SLC) family and ATP binding cassette (ABC) family. Widely studied ABC family transporters include P-glycoprotein (P-GP), breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP), and multidrug resistance proteins (MRPs). SLC family transporters related to drug transport mainly include organic anion-transporting polypeptides (OATPs), organic anion transporters (OATs), organic cation transporters (OCTs), organic cation/carnitine transporters (OCTNs), peptide transporters (PEPTs), and multidrug/toxin extrusions (MATEs). These transporters are often expressed in tissues related to drug disposition, such as the small intestine, liver, and kidney, implicating intestinal absorption of drugs, uptake of drugs into hepatocytes, and renal/bile excretion of drugs. Most of therapeutic drugs are their substrates or inhibitors. When they are co-medicated, serious drug-drug interactions may occur due to alterations in intestinal absorption, hepatic uptake, or renal/bile secretion of drugs, leading to enhancement of their activities or toxicities or therapeutic failure (5).

DRUG INTERACTION CHECKERS

There are several available free Drug Interaction Checkers (DICs) on the internet, as well as applications for mobile phone, such as Drug Interaction Checker on Drugs.com, Multi-Drug Interaction Checker Medscape, Drug Interaction Checker WebMD, as well as more detailed DICs such as Lexicomp (UpToDate) and Micromedex.

EXAMPLES OF IMPORTANT DRUG INTERACTIONS

Alcohol. Chronic alcoholism results in enzyme induction. Acute alcoholic intoxication tends to inhibit drug metabolism. Severe alcohol-induced hepatic dysfunction may inhibit ability to metabolize drugs. In the case of acetaminophen, there is an increased formation of hepatotoxic acetaminophen metabolites in chronic alcoholics. Patients who take oral anticoagulants may have increased hypoprothrombinemic effect with acute alcohol intoxication. Central nervous system depressants have additive or synergistic effect with alcohol on central nervous system depression. Acute alcohol intake may increase hypoglycemic effect of insulin, especially in fasting patients. In patients that take acitretin and drink alcohol there may be an increased conversion of acitretin to etretinate. Etretinate is teratogenic. Drugs that may produce a disulfiram-like reaction are cephalosporins, chloral hydrate, disulfiram, metronidazole and sulfonyleureas.

Oral anticoagulants. These drugs are metabolism inducible and susceptible to inhibition of CYP2C9-mediated metabolism. Oral anticoagulants highly bound to plasma proteins. Drugs that may increase anticoagulant effect are acetaminophen, amiodarone, anabolic steroids, chloramphenicol, cimetidine, clofibrate, clopidogrel, danazol, dextrothyroxine, disulfiram, erythromycin, fluconazole, fluoxetine, gemfibrozil, lovastatin, metronidazole, miconazole, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, propafenone, quinidine, salicylates, sulfapyrazone, sulfonamides, thyroid hormones, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, voriconazole, alcohol and allopurinol. Drugs that may decrease anticoagulant effect are aminoglutethimide, barbiturates, bosentan, carbamazepine, cholestyramine, glutethimide, nafcillin, phenytoin, primidone, rifabutin, rifampin, St. John's wort and oral hypoglycemics.

Digitalis glycosides. Digoxin is susceptible to alteration of gastrointestinal absorption. Digitalis toxicity may be increased by drug-induced electrolyte imbalance (hypokalemia). Digitoxin is metabolism inducible. Renal and non-renal excretion of digoxin is susceptible to inhibition. Drugs that may increase digitalis effect are amiodarone, azithromycin, clarithromycin, diltiazem (additive AV conduction effect), erythromycin, potassium-depleting drugs (increased likelihood of digitalis toxicity), propafenone, quinidine, spironolactone and

verapamil (additive AV conduction effect). Drugs that may decrease digitalis effect are kaolin-pectin, rifampin and sulfasalazine.

NSAID. Prostaglandin inhibition may result in reduced renal sodium excretion, impaired resistance to hypertensive stimuli and reduced renal lithium excretion. Most NSAIDs inhibit platelet function and thus, may increase likelihood of bleeding due to other drugs that impair hemostasis. NSAIDs decrease hypertensive response to ACE inhibitors, angiotensin II receptor blockers, hydralazine and decrease hypertensive, diuretic and natriuretic response to furosemide and thiazide diuretics. NSAIDs may increase methotrexate toxicity. Combined with SSRIs they may increase risk of bleeding due to platelet inhibition (6).

CONCLUSION

Drug interactions are very important cause of morbidity and mortality. Today's availability of OTC drugs and increased self-medication emphasizes the need of physician's awareness. Detailed pharmacological anamnesis with drug interaction checkup should be a part of every pharmacological anamnesis, both in primary care settings and in hospitals. Very important factor in preventing polypharmacy is good education of patients, especially when it comes to OTC drugs and self-medication. Good communication between physician and patient is crucial in establishing high quality polypharmacy in patients with comorbidities. It may be useful to create a mobile application for patients, a simplified patient-oriented Drug Interaction Checker, so that patients can check themselves drug-drug interactions before buying a new OTC drug. Drug Interaction Checkers for professionals are based on generic name of the drug, thus making it difficult for the patient's use. Patient-oriented Drug Interaction Checker should be made using Brand Name of the drug, so that the patient can easily check for interactions. Possible problems in establishing good control of polypharmacy and drug interactions are financial, institutional, organizational and lack of time.

REFERENCES

1. Bushardt RL, Massey EB, Simpson TW, et al. Polypharmacy: misleading, but manageable. *Clin Interv Aging*. 2008;3(2):383-9.
2. Masnoon N, Shakib S, Kalisch-Ellett L, Caughey GE. What is polypharmacy? A systematic review of definitions. *BMC Geriatr*. 2017;17(1):230.
3. Lynch SS. Drug Interactions. Jul 2019. Retrieved from <https://www.msdmanuals.com/>

professional/clinical-pharmacology/factors-affecting-response-to-drugs/drug-interactions
(Accessed on September 8, 2021)

4. Youdim A. Nutrient-Drug Interactions. May 2019. Retrieved from <https://www.msdmanuals.com/professional/nutritional-disorders/nutrition-general-considerations/nutrient-drug-interactions>
(Accessed on September 8, 2021)
5. Liu X. Transporter-Mediated Drug-Drug Interactions and Their Significance. *Adv Exp Med Biol.* 2019;1141:241-291.
6. Horn JR. Important drug interactions and their mechanisms. In: Katzung BG, Masters SB, Trevor AJ. *Basic and clinical pharmacology.* McGraw-Hill;2012.p.1149- 1162.